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How can we reduce the ‘messiness’ of the research-policy interface?

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Executive summary

Research can take a long time to influence policy decisions, typically going through circuitous routes in the process. This can discourage both researchers and policymakers from pursuing the laudable principles of evidence-based policymaking. Contributing to ISBE’s commitment to bring together academics, practitioners and policymakers, this Insight explores how the timeliness and effectiveness of the research-policy interface can be improved.

Steve Johnson has been engaged in policy-related research for over three decades. He reflects on his experiences and suggests a way forward, including expansion of co-created research, a more porous interface between research and policy careers, and commitment to open and constructive discussion of potentially contentious research and policy issues.

Why is the policy impact of research so ‘messy’, and what can we do about it?

Entrepreneurship and small business policy is inherently complex in terms of types of intervention, objectives, focus, target groups and spatial scale. Likewise, entrepreneurship and small business research is a broad church, as illustrated by the 13 (and growing) [ISBE Special Interest Groups](#). It is therefore not surprising that the relationship between research and policy in our field is complex and disparate. This means that policymakers may not be aware of research that might help them reach evidence-informed decisions; conversely researchers may be unaware of current and future policy priorities.

This is not unique to entrepreneurship and small business research and policy. Researchers and practitioners in fields such as health, environment and criminology have long explored the relationship between research, practice and policy, publishing in journals such as [Evidence and Policy](#). The ISBE community can learn lessons from this work and develop structures and ways of working that address some of the barriers that constrain effective research-policy interaction.

The policy impact of entrepreneurship and small business research

Entrepreneurship and small business research and policy are relatively young, having emerged as significant areas of interest in the early to mid-1980s. The author started his research career in 1986 and can provide a long-term perspective on the research-policy interface. In a recent article (Johnson, 2022) and [blog](#), Steve identifies a relationship between research and policy at the UK national level. However (1) this relationship is long-term in nature; (2) it is often research that is critical of prevailing policies that has such impact; (3) impact appears to occur through the accumulation of a body of scholarly work, rather than through individual projects or publications (Weiss, 1979). This means that linear conceptions of research impact do not help us to understand the process, which is messy and therefore difficult to pin down and measure (Figures 1 and 2).

Figure 1: Linear model of research impact

Source: Johnson (2022)

Figure 2: The messy reality of research impact

Source: Johnson (2022)

In response to Steve’s article, Kiran Trehan (2023) highlighted the potential significance of engaged scholarship and co-creation as mechanisms to improve policy impact, and Matt Flinders (2022) highlighted the contribution of initiatives such as the [Research on Research Institute](#) and the [Universities Policy Engagement Network](#). He also notes that research (but not all of it) might be expected to influence public policy, but that the work of academics should not be driven exclusively by immediate policy priorities. This is in line with ISBE’s philosophy and approach.

A way forward

There is much still to learn about the policy impact of entrepreneurship and small business research. The development of databases such as [Overton](#) provide an opportunity for more systematic analysis than has been possible to date. The messy relationship between research and policy may obscure examples of policy impact - as illustrated by the current author’s work - and raises questions about how to make the process less messy. Institutions such as ISBE can play a role in reducing this messiness and facilitating open and mutually beneficial interactions between researchers and policymakers.

Many commentaries on research impact urge researchers to communicate their findings and recommendations to policymakers in ‘understandable’ language. While these calls have merit, it is equally important to maintain high standards of integrity and rigour in research. This means that in depth theoretical, methodological and technical discussions at conferences such as ISBE remain necessary and important.

Nonetheless, there are some potential ways of addressing the messiness of the relationship between research and policy, to which ISBE and similar organisations might contribute:

- Encouraging and supporting genuine engaged scholarship and co-creation (Trehan, 2023) of research between academics and policymakers.
- Introducing more initiatives to enable academics to spend time in policy organisations and *vice versa*, without adversely affecting their career prospects, as part of wider moves towards a more '[porous academy](#)'.
- Changes in culture to enable the creation of shared and safe spaces in which academic researchers and policymakers can debate issues openly, including research that may challenge prevailing academic and policy thinking.

ISBE is in a strong position to take forward these ideas in relation to entrepreneurship and small business research and policy. Recent changes in the UK policy environment - such as greater regional devolution - provide a perfect opportunity to reimagine the research-policy ecosystem.

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